

TO STUDY THE EFFICACY OF AGNIKARMA IN FROZEN SHOULDER AS ANALGESIC COMPARISON TO TRAMADOL***¹Dr. Bharati Biswas, ²Dr. Namita Baishya**¹PG Scholar, Dept. of Shalya Tantra, Govt. Ayurvedic College, Guwahati-14.²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Shalya Tantra, Govt. Ayurvedic College, Guwahati-14.

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ABSTRACT

Pain and stiffness in the shoulder joint is the cardinal feature of frozen shoulder. But along with pain, there is restricted range of motion for which patient generally approaches a doctor. Acharya sushrut has mentioned agnikarma for very severe painful condition of skin, muscles, veins, nerves, joints and bones. 60 patients of frozen shoulder were selected from OPD, IPD of shalyatantra department as well as casualty of govt. Ayurvedic college and hospital guwahati after doing all the required investigations. **Aim & objective:** To study the efficacy of agnikarma in frozen shoulder as analgesic comparison to tramadol. **Materials & method:** 60 patients with frozen shoulders were taken in 2 groups of 30 patients each. Control group was administered tramadol 50mg orally 8 hourly for 5 days. Trial group was treated with agnikarma therapy using Panchadhatu shalaka 3 sittings alternately done

for 5 days. Panchadhatu shalaka was heated up to red hot by using gas stove and used for agnikarma after cleaning the affected area with triphala kwath. A bindu type of agnikarma was done followed by application of mixture of ghritha & madhu, after that yastimadhuurna was sprinkled over the affected area for its cooling effect. **Result:** pain intensity and duration, tenderness intensity and duration reduced completely after 3 sittings of agnikarma therapy. The results obtained were subjected to statistical analysis. **Discussion:** Agnikarma is simple, less invasive, safe & cost-effective procedure. Agni possesses ushna, tikshna, sukshma and ashukari gunas. It neutralizes the sheeta guna of vata and kapha dosha. Removes the srotovaharodha which occurred due to avaran of vikrita kapha. Heat increases the blood circulation

to the localized pathology, increases the dhatwagni so metabolism of dhatu becomes proper and promotes proper nutrition. Thus, pain in the affected area is quickly relieved. **Summary & conclusion:** Overall study showed that the agnikarma therapy gives better results than use of opioid analgesic tramadol. Acute pain (within 3 months) was treated better than chronic pain (within 6 months).

KEYWORDS: *Agnikarma, Panchadhatushalaka, Frozen Shoulder, Tramadol.*

INTRODUCTION

अंसदेशस्थितो वायुः शोषयित्वांसबन्धनम । शिराश्चाकुञ्चय तत्रस्थो जनयत्यवबाहुकम ॥

॥ Su.Ni.1/82 ॥^[1]

Avabahuka often known as 'Frozen Shoulder's is a disease that usually affects the amsa sandhi (shoulder joint). It is produced by the vata Dosha. Even though the term Avabahuka is not mentioned in the nanatmaja vata vyadhi, acharya sushruta & others have considered Avabahuka as a vataja vikara. Amsa sosha (wasting of the shoulder) can be considered as the preliminary stage of the disease, where loss or dryness of sleshaka kapha from amsa sandhi occurs.

According to the WHO, the prevalence of frozen shoulders is between 2 to 5 % of the general population. Females are more prone to disease than male. The incidence of frozen shoulders is 2- 4 times higher in diabetes than the general population.

In Frozen shoulder, there is pain & stiffness in the shoulder joint. It is distinguished by a restricted range of motion as well as discomfort that lasts for at least two months after the onset of the condition. In Sushrut Samhita, the word pain is mentioned as Ruja, ruka, Toda, vedana, Shoola.

There are different treatment modalities in Ayurveda, which are described by acharyas. Agnikarma is one among them. Acharya Sushrut has mentioned Agnikarma for very severe pain in the skin, muscle, veins, ligaments, bony joints and bones.

त्वङ्गंससिरास्नायुसन्ध्यस्थिस्थितेऽत्युग्ररुजि ॥

॥ Su.Su.12/10 ॥^[2]

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

- To evaluate the analgesic effect of Agnikarma in Frozen shoulder comparison to Tramadol.
- To conduct conceptual study of Agnikarma.
- To evaluate role of Agnikarma on pain
- To establish an alternative, non-invasive, non-medicative, Ayurvedic procedure for pain management in Frozen shoulder.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Plan of study

- Diagnosed cases of frozen shoulder will be registered after getting ethical clearance.
- CTRI registration will be applied after getting ethical clearance.
- Informed consent will be taken before conducting the trial.
- A separate case record proforma will be prepared for the study.
- Failure cases will be recorded and given other necessary treatment; the unattended cases will be excluded from the study.
- Two groups will be taken for the study.

MATERIALS

- Panchadhatu Shalaka
- Ghee
- Honey
- Yasthimadhu churna
- Triphala kwatha
- Sterile gloves
- Sterile gauge

METHODOLOGY

- Subjects:** The Study will be performed with 60 cases of frozen shoulder.
- Selection of patients:** All the patients will be randomly selected from OPD & IPD, Department of Shalya Tantra, GACH and will be registered for the study.

CLINICAL STUDY

- Research design: Open randomized trials
- Sample size: 60

- Study setting: IPD & OPD of Shalya tantra, GACH
- No. of Groups: 02
- Duration: 5 days including 3 sitting of Agnikarma.

GROUPING

- Group A: Agnikarma will be done in 30 numbers of diagnosed cases of frozen shoulder, 3 sitting alternate days up to 5 days.
- Group B: 30 numbers of patients of frozen shoulders will be treated with Tramadol 50mg/8 hourly for 5 days, orally.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Selection of patient was done irrespective of sex and religion.
- Patient with classical signs and symptoms of Frozen shoulder, i.e., Pain, Stiffness and restricted movements of the shoulder joint.
- Patient between age Group of 16 and 70 years.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Pain due to localized acute fracture
- Pain related to Cancer
- Uncontrolled Diabetes mellitus and Hypertension
- Subluxations or recurrent dislocations of the shoulder joint.
- Patients contraindicated for Agnikarma mentioned in Sushrut Samhita
- Pregnant lady, elderly people, children

LABORATORY INVESTIGATION

- Blood Routine Test
- Blood urea & Serum creatinine
- Blood Sugar-Fasting & Post prandial
- Viral Profile- HIV, Anti HCV, HBsAg
- X-ray of the specific part as required

METHOD

Procedure of Agnikarma

Poorva karma

- Examine patients thoroughly for sickness, vital spot (marma sthana), and strength.

- After discussing the procedure and its complications, the patient provided signed consent for the treatment.
- Confirm Agnikarma spot and use of a marker pen to highlight the site of maximal tenderness.
- Proper patient positioning
- Triphala kwath was used to clean the targeted spot. The space was covered with a sterile drape sheet.
- The tip of the Shalaka till is red hot.

Pradhan karma

- Precautions were taken during Agnikarma, particularly near sensitive areas such as the head, eyes, and delicate parts. And one should cover the eye with a piece of cloth.
- After that, Bindu Agnikarma (5-15 dots) was applied with red hot panchadhatu Shalaka to the indicated point.
- To lessen the burning sensation, a honey and ghrita mixture was applied during the procedure.
- Proper precautions were taken to prevent Asamyakdagdhavrana (burns that are not excessively superficial or deep).

Paschat Karma

- A small bandage was applied when the therapy was completed and the wound was cleaned with Yasthimadhuurna.
- The patient was instructed to remove the bandage next day and prevent water contact on the wound for 48 hours.
- The patient was told to review the next day.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Assessment will be done as per Universal Pain Assessment tool consist of Wong Baker facial Grimace Scale and activity tolerance test with gradation.

- Subjective criteria - Pain & stiffness.
- Objective criteria - Tenderness & range of movement (Flexion, Abduction, External rotation, Internal rotation, Extension, Circumduction)

SUBJECTIVE CRITERIA**Pain**

- No pain - 0
- No pain at rest, but pain occur on normal activity - 1
- Mild pain at rest, prevents some activities - 2
- Moderate pain at rest, interferes activities with concentration - 3
- Severe pain at rest, intolerable pain, prevents daily activity and verbal communication - 4

Visual Analogue scale: (1-10)

- 0 - No pain
- 1-3 - mild pain
- 4- 6 - Moderate
- 8-10 - Severe

Stiffness

- No stiffness - 0
- Mild stiffness (stiffness with movement on and off and does not interfere with routine work) - 1
- Moderate stiffness (stiffness on movements and does not interfere with routine work) - 2
- Severe stiffness (stiffness on movements as well as on rest which interfere with routine work) - 3
- Very Severe stiffness (interfering with most daily activities and requiring significant limitations or assistance) - 4

OBJECTIVE CRITERIA**Tenderness**

- No tenderness - 0

- Mild/Tolerable tenderness on deep palpation - 1
- Pain on ordinary palpation, patient does not prefer to tolerate - 2
- More intolerable pain on light palpation - 3
- Severe pain where patient doesn't allow to touch the affected area caused by even a stimulus like a sheet of paper - 4

Range of Movement

Flexion (0- 180°)	Abduction (0- 180°)	External rotation (0- 90°)	Extension (0- 60°)	Internal rotation (0- 90°)	Circumduction (0- 360°)
• Complete flexion (180°) = 0	• Full free (180°) = 0	• Full free (90°) = 0	• Full free (60°) = 0	• Full free (90°) = 0	• Full free (360°) = 0
• Above 120° = 1	• Above 120° = 1	• Above 50° = 1	• Above 45° = 1	• Above 50° = 1	• Above 180° = 1
• 90°-120° = 2	• 60°-120° = 2	• 25°-50° = 2	• 25°-45° = 2	• 25°-50° = 2	• 90°-180° = 2
• Up to 90° = 3	• Up to 60° = 3	• Up to 25° = 3	• Up to 25° = 3	• Up to 25° = 3	• Up to 90° = 3
• No flexion = 4	• No abduction = 4	• No external rotation = 4	• No extension = 4	• No internal rotation = 4	• No circumduction = 4

DURATION

- Symptoms relieved on 1st day/1st sitting - 0
- Symptoms relieved on 2nd day - 1
- Symptoms relieved on 3rd day/2nd sitting - 2
- symptoms relieved on 4th day - 3
- symptoms relieved on 5th day/3rd sitting - 4

CRITERIA FOR WITHDRAWAL

- Aggravation of disease symptoms
- If there is no improvement after 1st sitting
- Discontinuation by patient
- Development of complications

OBSERVATIONS

Table 1: Distribution of Frozen Shoulder Patients according to observation of parameters.

Parameter	Patients Predominant	Percentage
Age	41-50 Years (21 nos.)	34.99%
Gender	Female (33 nos.)	54.99%
occupation	Homemakers (19 nos.)	31.67%
Religion	Hinduism (55 nos.)	91.67%

Nature of work	Moderate (32 nos.)	53.33%
Socio-Economic status	Lower middle class (27nos.)	45%
Diet	Non-vegetarian (47 nos.)	78.34%
Severity of Pain (Acc. To VAS)	Moderate Pain (VAS 4-6) (33 nos.)	54.99%
Chronicity of Pain	> 1 month (25 nos.)	41.67%
Mode of Injury	Trauma (fall, injury) (24 nos.)	40%
Nature of Pain	Pain in normal activity (30nos.)	50%

In the series of 60 patients, 34.99% of them belonged to age group of 41-50 years with female predominance of 54.99% and Hindu religion predominance of 91.67%. On Screening, occupation homemakers ranked 31.67% with moderate work predominance of 53.33%. Maximum patients belong to lower middle-class group with predominance of 45% and non-vegetarian with predominance of 78.34%. Taking into the Severity of pain according to VAS, 54.99% of them had moderate pain (VAS 4-6) and in Chronicity of pain, 41.67% belongs to the group > 1 months. Trauma (fall or injury) was the most common cause with predominance of 40% and the pain was more in normal activity with predominance of 50%.

Table 2: Statistical analysis showing the result on clinical features after 5 days of treatment with Agnikarma.

SYMPTOMS	MEAN SCORE		% OF RELIEF	S.E(±)	't'	'p'
	BT± S.D	AT± S.D				
PAIN	2.83±0.65	0.47±0.51	83.39%	0.102	23.3121	<0.0001**
STIFFNESS	2.13±0.73	0.40±0.50	81.22%	0.106	16.2763	<0.0001**
TENDERNESS	3.00±0.64	0.53±0.51	82.34%	0.093	26.6260	<0.0001**
RANGE OF MOVEMENT						
a) FLEXION	2.50±0.78	0.57±0.57	77.2%	0.082	23.5435	<0.0001**
b) ABDUCTION	2.63±0.72	0.70±0.53	73.38%	0.082	23.5435	<0.0001**
c) EXTERNAL ROTATION	2.13±0.78	0.53±0.57	75.12%	0.091	17.5879	<0.0001**
d) INTERNAL ROTATION	1.53±0.82	0.43±0.50	71.89%	0.100	11.000	<0.0001**
e) EXTENSION	2.23±0.73	0.67±0.55	69.95%	0.092	17.0265	<0.0001**
f) CIRCUMDUCTION	2.70±0.60	0.80±0.55	70.37%	0.121	15.7257	<0.0001**

**Statistically significant, SD: Standard deviation, SE: Standard error, BT: Before treatment, AT: After treatment.

The table shows the percentage of improvement in the clinical features of Frozen Shoulder as Pain by 83.39%, Stiffness by 81.22%, Tenderness by 82.34% along with increase of range of movement.

RESULT

The Study showed that there is improvement in Pain by 83.39%, Stiffness by 81.22%, Tenderness by 82.34% along with more than 70% increase in overall range of movement.

DISCUSSION

Avabahuka is a Vatavyadhi as per Ayurveda literature, and their site is Amsa sandhi (Shoulder joint). Avabahuka has features like Pain, Stiffness And decreased range of motion that are nearer to those of a Frozen shoulder, a musculoskeletal disorder. Avabahuka affects the day-to-day activities of people, which finally affects the quality of life. In Sushruta Samhita, Acharya describes about the procedure of Agnikarma. The Ayurvedic treatment modality Agnikarma is basically a heat therapy and is able to pacify vata and kapha. Acharya Sushruta has mentioned agnikarma for very severe pain in the skin, muscles, veins, ligaments, bony joints and bones. Here in this study, we applied Agnikarma therapy in Shoulder joint as mentioned by acharya Sushruta with sepecial reference to Frozen Shoulder.

The present study has been undertaken to analysis the observations made before treatment by Agnikarma therapy, and the result obtained after treatment in Frozen Shoulder in comparison to observations made before treatment by Tramadol and the result obtained after treatment by the same in Frozen Shoulder.

- In this Study total 60 patients were registered based on the inclusion parameters and there were no drop cases. Those patients were randomly divided into two groups. One being treated with Agnikarma therapy including 3 sitting alternate days upto 5 days and other group treated with oral application of tablet Tramadol 50mg/8hrly for 5 days.
- According to Ayurveda, action of Agnikarma may be accessed by the properties of agni. Agni possesses ushna, laghu, sukshma and teekshna guna. By virtue of these guna Agnikarma works deep in tissue and removes obstruction in the srotas and increase in rasa rakta samvahana to the affected site. Ushna guna agni improves dhatwagni that pacifies the ama dosha and reduces pain – vata shamana.
- According to modern, with the application of Agni (heat)-
 - It raised local temperature.
 - Improves local blood circulation at the affected site.
 - Increase tissue metabolism and tissue regeneration process.
 - Clearance of accumulated metabolic waste.
 - Resolve inflammation and decrease local infection

- Reduces joint stiffness and tenderness.
- Causes relaxation of muscle and improves local healing process.

CONCLUSION

- Overall study showed that Agnikarma therapy has shown significant improvement in reducing pain and tenderness.
- Agnikarma therapy not only reduces pain & tenderness but also Increases range of motion.
- In this study, acute pain was treated more frequently than chronic pain in agnikarma therapy, and the results were better.
- The therapy has proven to be safe, simple and cost effective and no adverse effects were observed during the study.

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